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ABSTRACT

This international scientific journal is created for new scientific research.

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- social directions
- directions of philology
- pedagogic directions
- directions of discovery and invention
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GRAMMAR-TRANSLATION METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation. This article discusses easy ways to learn English grammar and translate. Grammar – translation classes are usually conducted in the students' native language. Grammatical rules are learned deductively; students learn grammar rules by rote, and then practice the rules by doing grammar drills and translating sentences to and from the target language. More attention is paid to the form of the sentences being translated than to their content. When students reach more advanced levels of achievement, they may translate entire texts from the target language. Tests often involve translating classical texts.

Key words: English language, article, grammar discusses, methods, classical language.

Аннотация. В этой статье обсуждаются простые способы изучения английской грамматики и перевода. Занятия по грамматике и переводу обычно проводятся на родном языке студентов. Грамматические правила изучаются дедуктивным путем; студенты изучают правила грамматики наизусть, а затем практикуют правила, выполняя грамматические упражнения и переводя предложения на целевой язык и с него. Больше внимания уделяется форме переводимых предложений, чем их содержанию. Когда студенты достигают более продвинутых уровней успеваемости, они могут переводить целые тексты с целевого языка. Тесты часто включают перевод классических текстов.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, статья, обсуждение грамматики, методы, классический язык.

The grammar translation method is a method of teaching foreign languages derived from the classical method Greek and Latin. In grammar-translation classes, students learn grammatical rules and then apply those rules by translating sentences between target language and the native language. The method has two main goals : to enable students to read and translate literature written in the target language , and to further students' general intellectual development . In this method of students learn much vocabulary in the form of lists. Student's should be taught in their mother

tongue. Method (GTM). Grammar Translation Method is a very traditional method. Grammar translation method was called the classical method since it was first used in the teaching of the classical language, Latin and Greek. The origin of this method lie in an attempt to teach languages by grammar and translation where the learners have to gather knowledge of foreign languages by studying a number of grammatical rules and applying these knowledge to the interpretation of texts with the use of a dictionary. Through the study of the grammar of target language, students would become more familiar with the grammar of their native language and that is familiarly would help them speak and write their native language better.[1] Memorization is amajor aspect of Grammar Transaction method. In GTM method the teacher gives something to memorize students and students have to memorize those consequently have to write.

As English teachers we are always on the lookout for effective and interesting ways to stimulate our language learners. Various teaching methods are aimed at this goal. The purpose of this report is to investigate the Translation Method that is widely used by a large number of teachers. This method is better known as the Grammar-Translation Method and considered to be a classical method of teaching English. The philosophy behind this method is that the foreign language can be taught or learn through translation. Here each phrase or sentence of English is taught by translating it into mother tongue. The Grammar-Translation Method instructs students in grammar and provides vocabulary with direct translations to memorize.

The Grammar-Translation Method derived from traditional approaches to the teaching of Latin and Greek and it was the predominant method in Europe in the 19th century. It was rather widespread for learning foreign languages, though by the end of the century moves towards the Direct Method were noticed.

The most relevant principles of this method can be summarized as follows:[2]

- It emphasizes the study and translation of the written language, as it is considered superior to spoken language.
- Reading and writing are the main language skills.
- The student's native language is the medium of instruction and used as well to compare with the language studied.
- The structural patterns of two languages are compared and this comparison makes learning more clear and firm.
- The fundamental principle of proceeding from known to unknown is followed throughout.

- Successful learners are those who translate each language into the other, though they cannot communicate orally.
- Students have to know verb conjugations and other grammatical paradigms.
- The knowledge of rules helps the learners to avoid any types of mistakes.
- Teachers play an authoritarian role in the classroom and the predominant interaction is between teacher-student.

The Grammar-Translation Method focuses on the teaching of the foreign language grammar through the presentation of rules together with some exceptions and lists of vocabulary translated into the mother tongue. Translation is considered to be the most important classroom activity.[3] The main procedure of an ordinary lesson follows this plan: a presentation of a grammatical rule followed by a list of vocabulary and, finally, translation exercises from selected texts.

Other activities and procedures can be the following: answering comprehension questions on the text; students find antonyms and synonyms words in the text; vocabulary is selected from the reading texts and memorized; sentences are formed using new words; fill-in-the-blank exercises; writing compositions on the topic.

This method has a number of advantages given below:

1. By telling the meaning of the word or sentence in mother tongue, the teacher can at once make the students understand.
2. The students are able to learn many items of English by comparison with mother tongue.
3. The comprehension of the students can be tested very easily.
4. Knowledge is acquired gradually, by traversing the facts of language and the syntactic mechanisms, going from simplest to the most complex.
5. Learning grammar, the students examine the texts developing awareness that language constitutes a system which can be analyzed.

There are some very obvious disadvantages of this method:

1. No account of present-day language usage is presented. Norms are imposed from the great literary authors.
2. Secondary grammatical points, lists of forms and examples receive a lot of attention; some definitions and explanations are often incoherent because of their heterogeneous criteria. Thus, facts about the language are confusing for the students.
3. It gives a predominant place to morphology but neglects syntax. Therefore, rules enabling the learners to construct systematically correct complex sentences are not presented.
4. Translations are often unsatisfactory as they are done word by word.

5. Students have to learn a lot of grammatical terms and too much weight falls on their memories. Frustration on the part of students and lack of demands on teachers are the effects of this method.

So, the teaching of grammar consists of a process of training in the language rules which must make it possible to all the students to express their opinion correctly, to understand the remarks which are addressed to them and to analyze the texts which they read. The objective is that by the time they leave college, the students control the tools of the language which are the vocabulary, grammar and the orthography, they are able to read, understand and write texts in various contexts. Unfortunately, this method gives little attention to listening and speaking skills, and the result is usually inability of some students to use the language for communication.

We find that this method has a few both merits and draw-backs. It can be successfully used at higher educational institutions for teaching foreign languages for professional communication, but it must be combined with other methods. We consider that the teachers should use a variety of methods to teach a second language as each student is unique and will respond well to a particular method. A good teacher should make use of the items that he or she has and the learning styles of the students. Adapting your style to your class can be an effective teaching method.

The Grammar-Translation method requires the learner to spend a lot of time understanding the language structure. Listening and speaking suffer because of this.

Understanding the structure is helpful in reading and particularly in writing. Grammar and vocabulary are emphasized throughout. This is the method of choice when the student's goal is to achieve a high level of writing and reading ability in a foreign language, versus speaking and listening.

The Audio-Lingual Method also allows the learner to communicate quickly but within the limited range that the repetition allows. It improves comprehension only if the speaker uses phrases that the learner has studied. Reading is limited, and an understanding of how to use the language is very limited. This is the method that is used when a live trainer is not available. The Direct Method gives the student the ability to communicate quickly because it is encouraged to be creative during practice. It gives, by far, the widest range of capability to understand what another person says to you and in developing your capability to speak. [3] This is the method of choice for instruction with a live trainer and where speaking and listening are most important.

Many theories about the learning and teaching of languages have been proposed. These theories, normally influenced by developments in the fields of linguistics and

psychology, have inspired many approaches to the teaching of second and foreign languages.

As statistics shows the Direct Method remained steady in a high usage . As it is considered to be more effective than the others . Because it gives more effort to speaking and listening which are considered to be essential while learning the second language.

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